

INITIAL LEGAL BASIS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF CITIZENS' SELF-GOVERNMENT BODIES IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Basic words: Bodies of self-government of citizens, neighborhood, city, village, village assembly of citizens, neighborhood assembly of citizens, chairman (elder) of the assembly of citizens, advisers, council of the assembly of citizens, assembly of citizens the inspection commission .

Abstract: In this article, with the honor of independence, comprehensive measures have been implemented in the field of restoration and further development of neighborhood authority in Uzbekistan, restoration of neighborhood values has been raised to the level of state policy, citizens' direct implementation of people's power, direct participation in state and community affairs. It has been considered that one of the tools of public participation, the main task of which is to ensure citizens' independent activities in solving issues of local importance, and the adoption of a number of decisions and decrees in this field.

With the honor of independence, extensive measures were taken in the field of restoration and further development of the authority of the neighborhood, as in all areas. Restoring neighborhood values has risen to the level of state policy.

One of the means of direct implementation of people's power, direct participation in state and community affairs, the main task of citizens is to ensure independent activities of citizens in solving issues of local importance.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens"[1] (April 22, 2013) specifies the legal status of self-governing bodies of citizens. According to this law, citizens' self-government bodies are:

- gathering of citizens of the neighborhood in the city, village and village;
- council of the citizens' assembly, commissions on the main directions of the citizens' assembly;
- inspection commission of citizens' meeting;
- an administrative commission established in the cases provided for by law in towns, villages and villages located far from the district center and difficult to reach.

Self-government bodies of citizens are not included in the structure of local government bodies. Self-government bodies of citizens enjoy the rights of a legal entity, have a model seal and must be registered with local government bodies.

About 10,000 citizen self-government bodies are active in Uzbekistan[4:1492-1495]. The election of citizens' assembly bodies and their officials is carried out by secret or open voting on the basis of general equal and direct suffrage, ensuring the guarantees of citizens' electoral rights established by law. The assembly of citizens is the highest body of self-government and has the right to represent the interests of the population and make decisions on its behalf in the relevant territory[5:135-138]. People who have reached the age of 18 and live permanently in the territory of the town, village, village, and neighborhood will participate in the meeting of citizens. The new version of the law "On Citizens' Self-Governing Bodies" specifies the powers of the township,

village [6:1-6], village assembly of citizens and the assembly of citizens of the neighborhood in the city.

The chairman (elder) of the citizens' assembly, his advisors, the main directions of the citizens' assembly, to implement the decisions of the citizens' assembly and to carry out the current activities of the citizens' self-government bodies during the interim period of the citizens' assemblies [7: 121-123], a council of the citizens' assembly will be established, consisting of the chairmen of the commissions and the responsible secretary of the assembly.

The audit commission is established to check the financial and economic activities of citizens' self-governing bodies. The administrative commission is established to consider cases related to administrative offenses within the scope of its powers.

In order to coordinate the activities of the self-government body of citizens [8:96-100], the council of elders of the republic, as well as regional, district, and city coordination councils for citizens' self-governance may be established.

The process of deepening democratic reforms in the system of local self-government in our country [9:128-131] is one of the most urgent tasks. Naturally, local self-government bodies ensure the participation of citizens in state administration and the implementation of public control, while closely helping to increase the efficiency of local administration.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the legal democratic state took part in the path of building a democratic state and the development of market relations. The problem of creating a legal state and civil society is closely related to the establishment of state power, the competent authorities of state power and the authorities of state power [10: 396-400]. These bodies form the people with the source of power.

Establishment and development of self-government of citizens, formation of its legal basis, fair citizenship in Uzbekistan's transition to democratic principles (principles) in the organization of society and the state and their activities A lot of work was done in the field of legislation and at the constitutional level [11:73-76] to establish the society. After all, only in the conditions of self-management, a sense of common interest and responsibility arises among citizens, citizens not only learn the methods of solving their own affairs, but at the same time take responsibility for solving the most important vital issues. also feels. In addition, citizens who have learned the lesson of self-governance can think objectively and competently about state policy.

In the Law "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" adopted on April 22, 2013, self-governance and independence of citizens are guaranteed by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Substance 1) , it is emphasized that self-government bodies are not included in the system of local state authorities (Substance 8).

Article 5 of the law specifies the main principles of the activities of citizens' self-government bodies: legitimacy, priority of human rights, freedoms and legal interests, democracy, transparency, social justice, independence in solving issues of local importance, public [12 :26-28] based on mutual assistance, social partnership, customs and traditions.

The fact that self-government is defined as a component (element) of the political system of society in Uzbekistan, together with the interests of individuals and the state, local interests are also recognized and guaranteed, which means that the local population (in cities, towns, villages and other places) population) is related to solving issues of direct provision of life and activities. At the same time, all these interests (society, state interests and local interests) are considered equal [3:59].

In this respect, the importance of self-management is manifested in various forms. It is a form of people's power; method of exercising civil rights; it can be defined as an organizationally and functionally separate institution in the system of society and state administration.

Let's briefly consider the importance of this institution. Self-government is a form of people's power. Along with state power, self-government represents the only people's power in Uzbekistan. Self-governing bodies in the exercise of their rights to institutions that directly express the will of the people (participation in elections and other events for self-governing bodies), as well as self-governing bodies and rely on their managers.

Creation, annexation, division and change of neighborhood is carried out by local state authorities at the initiative of citizens' self-government bodies ("Citizens' self-government bodies" Article 6 of the Law on Taking into account that the idea of rights and freedoms realized through self-management of citizens is diverse, in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this institution is interpreted on the basis of mutual relations with the individual [13:113].

On September 2, 1993, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Citizen Self-Government Bodies" was adopted, on April 19, 1999 and April 22, 2013, additions and amendments were made to this Law.

The law developed and clarified the system of self-government of citizens. Thus, this Law became the most important source of the right to self-government and the legal basis for its development.

In 2004, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On electing the chairman of the citizens' assembly and his advisers" was adopted. The norms of the right to self-government are stated in the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and government decisions. For example, the decree of September 12, 1992 "On the creation of the Republic "Mahalla" fund" [2]; Decree of February 23, 1998 "On support of citizens' self-government bodies"; Decree of January 23, 1999 "On increasing the role of citizens' self-management bodies in providing targeted social assistance to the population"; Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of April 19, 1999 on "Neighborhood Watchman" public structures, "On conciliation commissions under citizens' self-governing bodies" and other documents.

The volume of legal norms and guidelines has increased tremendously as a result of the growing importance of relations regulating the network of self-government rights. Now the number of citizens' self-government bodies in the Republic has reached 10,000, and the norms in this field are constantly improving. This situation also creates the need to develop legal regulations in the field of self-government from all sides[14:67].

Thus, the number of regulatory documents regulating self-management has increased significantly. In addition, relations between the norms of different branches of law, which differ from each other in terms of the subject and method of legal regulation of affairs in the field of self-governance, have become more intense and complicated. Perhaps, in the future, codification and incorporation of legal regulations applicable in the field of self-government may be necessary. This process also creates the need to form a separate legal branch of the right to self-governance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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